

Kinetics of Oxidation of L(-) β -Phenylalanine by Cerium(IV) in the Presence of Manganese(II) Ions

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Oxidation of L(-) β -phenylalanine by cerium(IV) sulphate in the presence of manganese(II) ions has been found to be first order in both, oxidant and L(-) β -phenylalanine concentrations. Various hypotheses for the mechanism of acid catalysis have been tested. The energy and entropy of activation have been calculated as 15.74 kcal mol⁻¹ and -18.24 kcal mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively. A tentative mechanism has been proposed in consistent with the experimental data.

A great deal of work has been done on oxidation of various inorganic compounds^{1,2} and organic compounds³⁻¹⁰ by Ce^{IV}. A careful survey of the literature reveals that kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by permanganate¹¹⁻¹³, chloramine-T¹⁴, peroxydisulphate¹⁷, metaperiodic acid¹⁸, and by potassium periodate¹⁹ have been reported. However, negligible attention has been paid to the oxidation of amino acids by Ce^{IV}²⁰⁻²². It undergoes oxidative decarboxylation in the presence of Mn^{II} ions only and, therefore, the present work was undertaken.

Experimental

L(-) β -Phenylalanine (E. Merck), ceric sulphate (Riedel), mangnous sulphate (B.D.H., A.R.) and other chemicals used were of B.D.H., A.R./S.M., G.R. grade. Double distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. The reaction vessels were coated with black paint to exclude any photochemical effect.

Solutions of sulphuric acid were standardised against previously standardised sodium hydroxide solution. The requisite amounts of L(-) β -phenylalanine, sulphuric acid and manganese(II) ions were taken in the reaction flask and kept in a thermostat at the desired temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The flask containing cerium(IV) sulphate solution was also kept in a thermostat. Requisite volume of cerium(IV) sulphate solution was then rapidly mixed. An aliquot (2 ml) was quenched in ferrous ammonium sulphate solution of known strength at different time intervals and then the remaining ferrous ions were titrated against ceric ions using ferroin as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied. It was observed that six equivalents of the cerium(IV)

ions consumed two equivalents of L(-) β -phenylalanine. Formation of ammonium ions and carbon dioxide was confirmed by the usual tests. Phenylacetaldehyde and phenylacetic acid were detected as the reaction products by spot-tests^{24, 25}. The induced reduction of mercuric chloride by the reaction mixture indicates the participation of free radicals²⁴.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE WITH L(-) β -PHENYLALANINE CONCENTRATION

[Ce^{IV}] = 5.0 $\times 10^{-3}$ M, [Mn^{II}] = 5.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ M
[H₂SO₄] = 1.0 M, Temp. = 308 K

L(-) β -Phenylalanine (M)	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
$k_1 (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$	4.68	8.09	10.75	12.94	14.89

When the concentrations of L(-) β -phenylalanine and sulphuric acid were in excess, the reaction followed a first order rate law. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant k_1 are listed in Table 1. The variation of ceric ions concentration had practically no effect on the rate constants, thus the order with respect to oxidant was unity. The effect of cerium(III) sulphate concentration on the reaction rate was also studied and it was observed that the reaction rate decreased with the increase in cerium(III) sulphate concentration.

The plot of log k vs log [L(-) β -phenylalanine] was found to be linear with a slope of 0.69 indicating the order of the reaction with respect to the substrate L(-) β -phenylalanine to be fractional. This provided a kinetic evidence for intermediate complex formation between the substrate L(-) β -phenylalanine and the oxidant, as the curve did not pass through the origin²⁶. The rate was found to decrease with the increasing concentration of sulphuric acid (Table 2). The rate also decreased with the increase in bisulphate ion concentration. Further, in an attempt to correlate the rate of

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TABLE 2—VARIATION OF RATE WITH H₂SO₄ CONCENTRATION

[L(-) β-Phenylalanine] = 0.15 M, [Ce^{IV}] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [Mn^{III}] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, Temp. = 308 K

H ₂ SO ₄ (M)	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
k ₁ (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	10.7	5.06	4.04	2.49	1.81

oxidation with acid concentration, various hypotheses for the mechanism of acid catalysis were tested. In this case, either of two Zucker—Hammett plots²⁶, was linear, indicating that the reaction was acid catalysed; however, none of these plots produced the ideal slope of unity. In view of these departures of ideal slope values, applicability of Bunnett hypothesis²⁷ and the Bunnett—Olsen LFER²⁸ were tested. The values of -H₀ and log a_{H₂O} corresponding to acid concentrations were taken from Paul and Long²⁹, and Bunnett³⁰, respectively. The values of the parameters ω, ω* and φ were found to be -26.4, -16.6 and 2.66, respectively. Primary salt-effect was not observed, but a linear plot of log k against ionic strength was obtained at higher concentration of added neutral salts. This indicated the involvement of at least a neutral molecule in the rate determining step of the reaction. The reaction was studied at different temperatures to evaluate the activation parameters (Table 3.)

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[L(-) β-Phenylalanine] = 0.15 M, [Ce^{IV}] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [Mn^{III}] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 M

ΔE‡ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS‡ kcal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	pZ × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
15.74	-18.24	1.034

The following probable mechanism explains the observed results.

The amino acid remains in protonated form in acid media,

The rate expression for this mechanism is therefore,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{HAA}^+][\text{Mn}^{III}][\text{Ce}^{IV}]}{[\text{H}^+][\text{Ce}^{III}]}$$

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